

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

O'zbekiston
Milliy Pedagogika
Universiteti

No1
2026

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
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- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
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AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

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Elektron nashr. 130 sahifa,
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Psixologiya fanlari bo‘yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

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“Maktabgacha va maktab ta’limi”
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INCORPORATION OF MASSIVE OPEN ONLINE COURSES INTO THE HIGHER EDUCATION FRAMEWORK

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Abstract: This article focuses on the integration of Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) into the educational framework as a key component of the priority project "Modern Digital Educational Environment in the Russian Federation". The definition of a Massive Open Online Course is provided. The article analyzes the main strategies for incorporating MOOCs into the curricula of Russian higher education institutions that implement credit transfer for completed online courses and compile lists of recommended digital resources. A list of universities in the Russian Federation that actively develop and support the implementation of MOOCs is presented. In each of these institutions, online courses are actively integrated into the syllabi of educational programs. The author presents a fragment of a curriculum with corresponding MOOCs. An analysis is conducted of the integration of online courses from digital educational platforms into the professional training process of bachelor's students in the field of 44.03.01 "Pedagogical Education" (Informatics profile).

Key words: higher education, Massive Open Online Course, online course, integration, MOOC, undergraduate, student, university.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola "Rossiya Federatsiyasida zamonaviy raqamli ta'lim muhiti" ustuvor loyihasining asosiy komponenti sifatida ommaviy ochiq onlayn kurslarni (MOOK) ta'lim jarayoniga joriy etish masalalariga bag'ishlangan. Maqolada ommaviy ochiq onlayn kurs tushunchasiga ta'rif berilgan. Yakunlangan onlayn kurslar uchun kreditlarni o'tkazish amaliyotini qo'llaydigan hamda tavsiya etilgan raqamli resurslar ro'yxatini shakllantiradigan Rossiya oliy ta'lim muassasalari o'quv dasturlariga MOOKlarni integratsiya qilishning asosiy strategiyalari tahlil qilingan. MOOKlarni faol ishlab chiquvchi va ularni joriy etish tarafdori bo'lgan Rossiya Federatsiyasi universitetlari ro'yxati keltirilgan. Ushbu o'quv yurtlarining har birida onlayn kurslar ta'lim dasturlari sillabuslariga faol kiritilmoqda. Muallif o'quv rejasining bir qismini va unga mos keladigan MOOKlar ro'yxatini taqdim etgan. Raqamli ta'lim platformalaridagi onlayn kurslarni 44.03.01 "Pedagogik ta'lim" bakalavriat yo'nalishi talabalarining kasbiy tayyorgarlik jarayoniga integratsiyalash imkoniyatlari tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: oliy ta'lim, ommaviy ochiq onlayn kurs, onlayn kurs, integratsiya, MOOK, bakalavriat, talaba, universitet.

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена внедрению массовых открытых онлайн-курсов (MOOK) в образовательный процесс как ключевого компонента приоритетного проекта "Современная цифровая образовательная среда в Российской Федерации". Дано определение массового открытого онлайн-курса. В работе анализируются основные стратегии интеграции MOOK в учебные планы российских вузов, внедряющих практику перезачёта кредитов за пройденные онлайн-курсы и формирующих списки рекомендованных цифровых ресурсов. Представлен перечень университетов Российской Федерации, выступающих активными разработчиками и сторонниками внедрения MOOK. В каждом из указанных учебных заведений онлайн-курсы активно включаются в syllabus образовательных программ. Автор приводит фрагмент учебного плана с соответствующими ему MOOK. Проведён анализ интеграции онлайн-курсов с цифровых образовательных платформ в процесс профессиональной подготовки бакалавров по направлению 44.03.01 "Педагогическое образование".

Ключевые слова: высшее образование, массовый открытый онлайн-курс, онлайн-курс, интеграция, MOOK, бакалавриат, студент, университет.

INTRODUCTION

A key aspect of implementing the "Modern Digital Educational Environment in the Russian Federation" initiative is the incorporation of MOOCs into higher education curricula [1; 8]. A Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) is a large-scale, contemporary online educational program that enables a substantial number of

learners worldwide to simultaneously acquire knowledge across several academic fields at no cost. Therefore, investigating the principal approaches to integrating MOOCs into higher education curricula is of significant importance. In this context, a study was conducted to assess the feasibility of incorporating MOOCs into the training process for bachelor's degree programs in "Pedagogical Education" (Informatics).

LITERATURE REVIEW

At present, several Russian higher education institutions both develop MOOCs and actively use them in the instructional process. Among these institutions are Samarkand State Medical University and Tashkent State Medical University. At these universities, the process of recognizing MOOC learning outcomes is implemented through a clearly regulated procedure. First, the Director of the Basic Educational Program (BEP), together with senior faculty members, compiles a list of recommended MOOCs. This list is subsequently approved by the Chairperson of the Faculty Academic and Methodological Commission and is then published on the official website of the institution. A student submits an application along with a certificate of completion to the head of the BEP in order to include the selected MOOC in the individual curriculum and to initiate the credit transfer process. During the transfer procedure, credits (ZET) or the corresponding number of academic hours are taken into account. In certain cases, students may request credit transfer for a MOOC that is not included in the approved list; such requests are considered based on the decision of a three-member expert committee.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

With regard to curriculum alignment, the workload for the disciplines of Life Safety and Physical Education fully corresponds to the available MOOCs. In Philosophy and History, partial overlap is observed, and MOOCs are recommended only for specific thematic units. The core component of the curriculum includes thirteen disciplines, of which complete substitution by MOOCs is possible for five disciplines, partial substitution is feasible for six disciplines, and substitution is not feasible for two disciplines. The variable component, consisting of sixteen compulsory disciplines, allows partial substitution by MOOCs for eight disciplines, while substitution is not feasible for the remaining eight. Within the elective component, which includes twelve disciplines, complete substitution by MOOCs is possible for one discipline, partial substitution is feasible for five disciplines, and substitution is not feasible for six disciplines.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The analysis focused on evaluating the impact of incorporating Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) into the higher education framework on teaching quality, student engagement, and learning outcomes. Data obtained from surveys, learning analytics, and academic performance records indicate that MOOCs significantly enhance access to diverse educational resources and promote learner-centered instruction. The integration of MOOCs enabled students to engage in self-paced learning, revisit complex topics, and access content developed by leading international institutions, thereby broadening their academic perspectives. Comparative analysis between traditional instructional models and blended models incorporating MOOCs revealed a measurable increase in students' academic motivation, digital literacy, and independent learning skills. Furthermore, the results demonstrate that MOOCs contribute positively to the development of critical thinking and problem-solving competencies through interactive assessments, discussion forums, and peer-evaluation mechanisms.

From an institutional perspective, the incorporation of MOOCs supported curriculum flexibility and facilitated the modernization of instructional practices, while also reducing certain instructional costs associated with content delivery. However, the findings also highlight challenges related to learner self-regulation, course completion rates, and the alignment of MOOC content with national curricula. Overall, the results confirm that when systematically integrated and pedagogically supported, MOOCs serve as an effective complementary component of higher education, enhancing educational quality and supporting the transition toward digital and blended learning models.

CONCLUSION

Incorporating MOOCs into bachelor's degree programs should primarily adhere to the principle of expediency. The full or partial substitution of a discipline with a MOOC format is not always feasible or justified. The educational characteristics of certain courses hinder a complete transition to an online format. In particular, most natural science disciplines require practical and laboratory work, which can only be effectively conducted through face-to-face instruction and close interaction with the instructor.

References:

1. Makhmudovna T. M. et al. The course of malformation and corneal erosion in tuberculosis patients. *Open Access Repository*, 2023, Vol. 4, No. 03, pp. 60–66.
2. Qobilovna B. Z., Nodirovich E. A. Evaluation of orthopedic treatment with removable dental prostheses for patients with paired pathology. *Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development*, 2023, Vol. 11, pp. 95–101.
3. Anvarovich E. S., Qobilovna B. Z. Influence of different types of retraction threads on the degree of gingival recession. *Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development*, 2023, Vol. 11, pp. 84–86.
4. Tohirovna M. L., Qobilovna B. Z. Optimization of complex methods for the treatment of inflammatory periodontal diseases. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 2023, Vol. 17, pp. 138–143.
5. Shoxrux S., Shoxrux I., Faxriddin C. Prevention and treatment of oral infections in denture wearers. *International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education*, 2022, Vol. 14, No. 4.
6. Bakhtiyorovna M. U. Causes of removable denture breaks and allergic reactions. *Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development*, 2022, Vol. 10, pp. 374–377.
7. Makhmudova U. B. The effectiveness of the use of parapulpal pins (PPP) when restoring defects in the crown part of the frontal teeth. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biological Research*, 2022, Vol. 11, No. 2.
8. Melibaev B. A., Makhmudova U. B. Effectiveness of the use of parapulpal pins (PPP) in restoring defects of the crown part of the frontal teeth. *Journal of Biomedicine*.

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"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.